

A Study on Building Brand Equity through Social Media Marketing

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Ramya, U., et al. “A Study on Building Brand Equity through Social Media Marketing.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science & Humanities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 15–20.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3575273>

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Abstract

In the era of digitalization most of the companies are investing in social media marketing to build and enhance the brand. Social media is becoming popular among the young generation; youngsters are engaged in social media for 24hr in a day. Social media marketing has the high impact on the brand equity and it is replacing the traditional marketing and brand equity helps the firms to sustainability and consumers loyalty towards the brand. The research paper highlights how social media marketing is building the brand equity of the products and the services. In this research paper researcher considered the honeycomb model for the social media and for brand equity Aaker, 1991 model is considered to analyse the data and conceptual model was developed by researcher to find the impact of social media marketing on brand equity. Primary data was collected through the questionnaire in the Bangalore city. The findings of the study will help to understand the role of social media marketing to build the brand equity.

Keywords: Social media, Brand equity, Branding, Consumers, Marketing.

Introduction

Last three decades brand equity has been recognized in the field of literature as the intangible asset to promote the performance of the organisation. Brand equity help the firm to build the brand loyalty, brand awareness and bringing profit to the organisation, (Joo-Eon Jeon 2017). Today in the business world CEO, Managers are struggling to sustain in the market and profit earning for the organisation. Building brand and brand equity will help the organisation to sustain and profit making by satisfied customer. Customers are very brand conscious and brand equity helps the customer to have brand awareness and the brand loyalty towards the brand. Brand equity is the trust and loyalty of the customer towards the brand. Brand helps the firms to differentiate its product and service from the competitors. Firms are investing and findings new ways to build the brand equity. Social media marketing is the best way to build brand equity in the era of digitalization where the customers are social media savvy. Social media made the firms to reach the customer regularly at any time and at any place.

Social media marketing helps the firms to bridge gap between the firm and the customer or we can say that it bridge gap between the virtual and the physical space. Young generations are spending minimum 10 to 12 hours in a day in the social media platform. Social media platform helps the firms to send the communication to the customer at any place and at any time. Social media marketing help to promote the brand through various social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter and the Pinterest. Social media marketing help the organisation to communicate directly to the customer and create brand awareness among the customers.

Very few studies have been conducted in India to analyse the role of social media marketing to build the brand equity. Researcher has analyzed the gap and conducted the research in Bangalore to find out the role of social media marketing to build the brand equity. The study has used the Honey comb model for the social media and for brand equity Aaker, 1991 model is considered to analyse the data. Jan H. Kietzmann, Bruno S. Silvestre, Ian P. McCarthy and Leyland Pitt (2012) in the research paper analyse the honeycomb model of seven blocks and framed the individual block questions to study the honey comb model. Researcher emphasis on the importance of the social media using the honey comb model and it can be helpful for the future research to find out the relationship between public affair and the social media.

Researcher has used the three factors of honeycomb model identity, sharing and relationship for the social media marketing and for brand equity consider the Brand awareness, brand loyalty, perceived quality and brand association.

Review of Literature

Nisha Anupama Jayasuriya, S. M. Ferdous Azam (2017) researcher in the research paper analyzed the impact of the Facebook on the brand equity. Researcher has constructed the new model to analyse the relationship between SMM and the brand equity based on the literature review. Dhanushanthini Ajanthan (2017) researcher in the research paper analyzed whether there is an impact of social media marketing to the brand equity in the tourism industry. Findings of the study reveals there is a positive impact of SMM over the brand equity in the tourism industry. Joo-Eon Jeon (2017) researcher in the research paper analyzed the relationship between brand concept and the brand equity. Researcher has considered emotional attachment and customer commitment to analyse the concept. The findings of the study suggest the positive impact of emotional attachment towards the brand and customer commitment. The study reveals that the brand equity is affected by the consumer commitment towards the brand. The study suggests that brand manager need to work on the building brand value among the consumers. Hamed Karamian (2015) in the research paper analyse the impact of social media on the brand equity. Finding of the study revealed the positive and significant impact of SMM on the brand equity. Study approves the positive effect of brand awareness, perceived quality and brand loyalty which indicates the social media can be used to build the brand equity to attract and retain the interest among the consumers. Bruno Godey (2016) analyzed the relationship between social media and brand equity in the luxury brand sector. Researcher in the research paper measures brands' social media marketing efforts as a holistic concept that incorporates five aspects entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and word of mouth. The finding of the study reveals that there is a significant effect of social media on the brand equity factors brand image and the brand awareness. As'ad, H. Abu-Rumman (2014) conducted the research to understand the relationship between the social media marketing and the brand equity. The findings suggest that the social media marketing has the positive and significant relationship with brand equity specifically for the mobile provider. Study indicated that usage of mobile users are using mobile application and using social media which helps the mobile provide to create awareness in the social media and to build the brand equity of their firm.

The honeycomb model has been introduced to the world by Smith (2007). He has adapted Morville’s user experience honeycomb model to the social media context. Seven social media building boxes can be identified as identity, presence, relationships, conversations, groups, reputation and sharing.

Objective of the Study

- To analyse the influence of identity over the brand equity
- To explore the impact of sharing and relationship on the brand equity
- To understand the impact of relationship in social media on the brand equity

Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: Social media identity has significant effect on the brand equity

Hypothesis 2: Sharing on social media and relationship has significant effect on the brand equity

Research Model

The research model includes social media and brand equity. Social media three factors identity, sharing and relationship has been considered and for the brand equity, four factors have been highlighted in this model, which are brand association, perceived quality, brand loyalty and brand awareness.

Conceptual Model

Findings and Analysis: Regression Analysis for Brand Identity (To find the Relationship between factors Influencing Brand Identity)

The above diagrams intercept the relationship between the factors influencing brand identity. In the first case, a Correlation & Regression Analysis is computed to know :

I. Relation between Reliability of respondents on the brand through its profile & the content shared by company’s brand on social media.

Correlation Analysis: Through R software, it was found that there was a strong & positive correlation (0.6827) between profile & the content shared by company’s brand on social media. Therefore, the relationship is established through high correlation.

Regression Analysis: As the correlation existed between profile & the content shared by company’s brand on social media, it was valid to check how strong their relationship was. Therefore, Regression Analysis was used to check this.

Estimated Slope

The Analysis showed the estimated slope of 0.76027 & confidence interval (95%) showed that slope lies between 0.59883763 & 0.9217103 that is the effect of content shared on social media on brand profile.

Standard Deviation: The residual error (SD) Is 0.5677 & is further displayed in the Figure above. The residual error shows a pattern on Standardized Residuals Axis which suggests that variance is non-linear & non-constant. The std.Error was close to zero (indication of strong relation)

Metrics to Identify the Regression Model

To identify the linear Regression model, p-Values are considered very important only when both p-Values are less that the pre-determined statistical significance level, which is ideally 0.05.

t-value indicates that it is less likely that the coefficient is not equal to zero p . So higher the t -value, higher the statistical significance.

In the analysis conducted, the F-statistic showed $87.3 > 0.80$ which is an indication that there is a relation between variables & null hypothesis is equal to zero. The p -value to hold true when the t -statistic must be greater than 1.96 for p -value to be 0.05. In the analysis conducted, the t -statistic was equal 9.343, which establishes the relation between variables.

II. Discovering the Impact of Previous Experience of users of Brand and Brand Uniqueness with Brand Equity

Correlation Analysis: The Correlation heat map shows that there is a weak relationship between Uniqueness of Brand & Past experiences of users of Brand. The Correlation was 0.3227443 indicating that customers don’t prefer brands because of its uniqueness & are buying them due to past experience. On analyzing the influence of Past usage in Brand on Satisfaction the respondents, it was found that a positive & weak correlation(0.2762377) existed between the variables which can be interpreted as the past usage of the brand by users doesn’t always give them satisfaction. The result indicates that there is positive relationship between the social media sharing and the brand equity. Marketers can use social media platform to share the images and content and regrams the content by consumer which helps to create brand aware ness and the brand equity.

The results shows that there was a strong & positive correlation between profile & the content shared by company’s brand on social media and company can use the social media to create brand identity on the social media. The result shows that there is a weak relationship between Uniqueness of Brand & Past experiences of users of Brand which indicating that customers don’t prefer brands because of its uniqueness & are buying them due to past experience.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to analyse the role of social media to build brand equity and results shows the positive relationship of social media marketing and brand equity. Marketers can use social media platform to market the brand as result shows that there is positive relationship between

the social media sharing and the brand equity. Marketers can use social media platform to share the images and content and regrams the content by consumer which helps to create brand awareness and the brand equity. There is a weak relationship between Uniqueness of Brand & Past experiences of users of Brand which indicating that customers don't prefer brands because of its uniqueness & are buying them due to past experience. This indicates that the consumers prefer the new brand than the old brand. Consumers prefer buying new brands so it indicates that the marketers need to create brand awareness in the social media.

References

1. Joo-Eon Jeon (2017) Joo-Eon Jeon, (2017) “The impact of brand concept on brand equity”, Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Vol. 11 Issue: 2, pp.233-245.
2. Nisha Anupama Jayasuriya, S. M. Ferdous Azam(2017) , The Impact of Social Media Marketing on Brand Equity: A Study of Fashion-Wear Retail in Sri Lanka,International Review of Management and Marketing, 2017, 7(5), 178-183.
3. Dhanushanthini Ajanthan (2017), The Role of a Social Media Marketing in Building Brand Equity- A Special Reference to Travel & Tourism Industry in Sri Lanka, Global Journal of Management and Business Research: E Marketing Volume 17, 31-37.
4. Jan H. Kietzmann¹, Bruno S. Silvestre, Ian P. McCarthy and Leyland Pitt(2012), Unpacking the social media phenomenon: towards a research agenda, Journal of Public Affairs (2012)
5. Hamed Karamian (2015) Do Social Media Marketing Activities Increase Brand Equity?, Int. j. econ. manag. soc. sci., Vol (4), No (3), March, 2015. pp. 362-365.
6. Bruno Godey (2016) Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on brand equity and consumer behavior, Article in Journal of Business Research • June 2016.
7. As'ad, H. Abu-Rumman (2014)The Impact of Social Media Marketing on Brand Equity: An Empirical Study on Mobile Service Providers in Jordan, Rev. Integr. Bus. Econ. Res. Vol 3(1)